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TRANSPORT AS CATALYST FOR POVERTY ALLEVIATION: LESSONS FOR NIGERIA FROM GLOBAL CASE STUDIES

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Abstract: *Transport systems play a critical role in shaping economic opportunities, social inclusion, and poverty outcomes. This study examined the relationship between transport and poverty alleviation in Nigeria, drawing on case studies from both urban and rural contexts, including the Lagos Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) system and the Rural Access and Mobility Project (RAMP). Using a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative case study analysis with quantitative data synthesis to examine transport's role in poverty alleviation, Systematic Literature Review, analytical Tools of SWOT analysis for benchmarking Nigeria's transport against global best practice, was employed in analysing the data. The study finds that while urban transport initiatives have improved job access and reduced travel times, limited coverage, affordability issues, and spatial mismatches persist. Rural areas face deeper connectivity challenges, where the lack of motorable roads significantly restricts access to education, healthcare, and markets. The findings concluded that transport affordability, spatial equity, and integrated policy frameworks are essential for sustainable poverty reduction. Recommendations included expanding affordable urban transit, prioritising cost-effective rural road infrastructure, and aligning transport investment with poverty reduction strategies.*

Keywords: transport poverty, poverty alleviation, rural connectivity, urban mobility, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Transport plays a pivotal role in economic, spatial, and social development, serving as a catalyst for migration and transformation. While economic growth is often linked to transport development, lack of transport infrastructure can constrain progress (Rodrigue, 2020). As Wilfred Owen aptly stated, "Immobility perpetuates poverty." Transport enables access to jobs, education, business, and social opportunities; without it, quality of life diminishes, and exclusion increases (Luke, 2024; Tiznado, Palm, & Farber, 2024). Beyond financial means, transport access depends on physical,

mental, and time resources (Olojede, Yoade, & Olufemi, 2017).

Accessibility and adequate transport infrastructure are critical in addressing urban poverty, which is linked to spatial, economic, and social exclusion (Chanieabate, He, Guo, Abrahamgeremew, & Huang, 2022). Edward Ullman's interaction model—regional complementarity, intervening opportunity, and spatial transferability emphasizes transport's role in connecting markets, fostering trade, and transitioning from isolated economies to open ones (Zahonogo, 2016). In both developed and developing nations, sustainable urban transport remains

a challenge, yet improving mobility for the poor is essential to achieving global development goals (Rodrigue, 2020).

Urban poverty, affecting nearly a quarter of the world's population and half in developing nations, is exacerbated by a lack of access to basic services (Rath, 2022; Tiznado et al., 2024). Interactions between mobility and poverty are dynamic, varying across and within cities (Dueñas, Campi, & Olmos, 2021). Inadequate transport infrastructure isolates the urban poor from markets, education, healthcare, and employment, reinforcing low income and poor health outcomes.

Historically, transport investments were assumed to reduce poverty, but evidence shows they often benefit the non-poor unless consciously designed for inclusivity. Road connectivity remains the primary means for poor to access services. Studies from Ethiopia, Ghana, Nepal, Uganda, and China show that basic rural road construction can significantly reduce poverty, improve school enrolment, and enhance service delivery, with higher returns than upgrading existing high-volume roads (Paul & John, 2014). Mobility involves both short-term travel choices and long-term decisions such as housing and employment locations (Shamshiripour, Rahimi, Shabanpour, & Mohammadian, 2020), and is especially critical for the poor as it can determine pathways out of deprivation. In Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation and among its poorest, most residents walk due to limited and unaffordable transport options (Lin, 2024). While paved roads would improve conditions, integrating public transit and alternative transport strategies could enhance access and reduce poverty. This study examined the role of transport in poverty alleviation globally, drawing lessons for Nigeria and offering policy recommendations with relevance to Africa and other urban poverty contexts.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This section examines transport poverty, the dynamics between transport and poverty, and relevant theories, specifically spatial mismatch and entrapment and social exclusion theory, which together frame the cycle of transport and poverty.

TRANSPORT POVERTY

Transport poverty describes situations where individuals or households cannot make essential journeys due to factors such as lack of car access, inadequate public transport, and rising fares (Sustrans, 2012a). While often linked to affordability, it is more complex than the cost of motoring alone. The Royal Automobile Club (RAC) Foundation (2012) adapted the fuel poverty definition—spending more than 10% of income on transport (DECC, 2013)—to classify households spending over 10% on transport as being in transport poverty. However, luxury spending (e.g., private cars, first-class travel) complicates this metric (Urry, 2007). Following Hills' 2012 review, fuel poverty definitions shifted to a Low-Income High Costs (LIHC) framework (Middlemiss, 2016).

Sustrans (2012a) proposed a composite transport poverty measure for England using three indicators: (1) time to essential services, (2) distance to nearest public transport, and (3) family income. While this identifies high-risk areas, it does not pinpoint individual households. Alternative terms include “poverty of access” (Farrington & Farrington, 2005), “transport wealth” (Lucas, 2011), and “transport hardship” (Cain & Jones, 2008). Lucas's (2011) “transport wealth” considers car availability, public transport access, and access to key services, enabling comparisons between households but not identifying unmet needs. Overall, defining and measuring transport poverty remains

challenging due to complex individual needs and limited national data.

DYNAMICS OF TRANSPORT AND POVERTY

Transport and social disadvantage are interlinked: limited access to travel, high fares, and poor information provision combine with low income, unemployment, poor housing, and limited skills to restrict opportunities (Lucas, 2012). Poor transport infrastructure can exacerbate these disadvantages, leading to social exclusion. Spatial mismatch theory explains how low-income residents—often concentrated in poorly served areas—face reduced job access and longer commutes (Castro, Ortega, & Odamtten, 2022). High dependence on walking exposes the poor to risks such as road accidents, pollution, and physical isolation from essential services. These distributional effects heighten the vulnerability of disadvantaged households to transport-related harms.

TRANSPORT AND POVERTY IN AFRICAN CITIES

The cycle of transport and poverty reflects the unequal social and spatial distribution of transport supply and externalities, producing social exclusion, spatial mismatches, and related effects (Lucas, 2012; Helena et al., 2014) (Figure 1). World Bank studies highlight four key transport disadvantages for Africa's urban poor: low public transport access, high reliance on informal modes, long distances between peripheral housing and jobs, and extensive walking, often unsafe with pedestrians comprising two-thirds of road fatalities (World Bank, 2004a, 2004b; Markovich & Lucas, 2011). These patterns are worsened by poverty, limited car ownership, and poor-quality, informal services (Mitric, 2013; Sietchiping et al., 2012). Affordability is a major barrier, especially for slum women and children,

preventing access to education and jobs (Alonso-Epelde et al., 2023). Public transport costs consume a significant share of poor households' budgets, creating "poverty traps" in peripheral settlements (Diaze et al., 2008; Panman & Gracia, 2022; Lucas, 2012).

Transport disadvantage extends beyond lack of infrastructure to time costs, safety risks, and discomfort, with disproportionate effects on women (Currie & Delbosc, 2011). Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) systems show potential to improve mobility and reduce informal transport reliance, but benefits often favour middle-income commuters, and affordability remains a barrier (Vas & Venter, 2012; Venter, 2011; Mitric, 2013). Residential location strongly influences expenditure, yet African cities rarely enable the poor to live near work, deepening economic vulnerability (Venter, 2011).

Four recurring themes emerge: income poverty, spatial mismatches, pedestrian safety, and gendered impacts (Salon & Gulyani, 2010). Most research stresses transport deficits and long-distance walking, with limited exploration of shelter-livelihood-transport strategies. Weak institutions, poor data, and fragmented planning persist, while the effects of pro-motorisation policies remain understudied.

SPATIAL MISMATCH THEORY

This theory links poverty to the geographic separation of jobs, housing, and transport (Liu & Bardaka, 2020). In contexts of suburbanisation, affordable housing is often poorly connected to jobs, making access difficult for low-income, car-less residents. Barriers stem from location patterns, limited transport alternatives, and affordability, sometimes compounded by skills mismatch or "spatial entrapment" for caregivers in low-wage, localised work (Levy, 2013). Limited transport access can hinder job

retention more than education or training (Blumenberg & Ong, 2001). Here, the theory explains that poverty is linked to transport, when affordable housing is poorly connected to jobs, making access difficult for low-income, car-less residents.

SOCIAL EXCLUSION THEORY

Focusing on the consequences rather than causes of transport deprivation, this perspective defines transport-related social exclusion as reduced ability to participate in

society due to insufficient mobility (Lucas, 2012; Helena et al., 2014). Beyond distance barriers, exclusion may result from physical, affordability, time, safety, or regulatory constraints (Church et al., 2000). Poor transport limits access to work, healthcare, education, and other life-enhancing activities, risking isolation and reduced well-being (Delbosc & Currie, 2010). According to Jones and Lucas (2012), Social exclusion approaches tend to promote holistic, integrated planning responses over purely spatial solutions (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Social Exclusion Model
Source: Jones and Lucas (2012)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study adopted a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative case study analysis with quantitative data synthesis to examine transport’s role in poverty alleviation. The Study was conducted in three phases:

1. **Systematic Literature Review** – Global cases from Kenya, South Africa, China, the UK, and the US were selected based on: (i) demonstrated poverty reduction

via transport interventions, (ii) relevance to Nigeria’s urbanization, rural–urban divides, or informal transport, and (iii) availability of longitudinal socioeconomic data. These were sourced from peer-reviewed journals, World Bank reports, and policy documents (2010–2023).

2. **Comparative Analysis** – Cross-case synthesis applied Lucas’s (2012) Transport Disadvantage Framework to assess *accessibility* (physical and

financial barriers), *affordability* (cost burden), and *socioeconomic outcomes* (employment, education, health).

- 3. **Nigeria-Specific Data Integration** – Key metrics (poverty headcount ratios, transport expenditure as a share of household income, and school enrolment rates in transport-deprived areas) were obtained from secondary sources, including the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Lagos Metropolitan Area Transport Authority (LAMATA), and Rural Access and Mobility Project (RAMP).

Analytical Tools included SWOT analysis for Bench-marking Nigeria’s transport against global best practice, and GIS mapping to visualize spatial mismatches in Lagos and Kano.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

NIGERIA CONTEXT ANALYSIS

Nigeria Context Analysis revealed urban challenges such as long commutes (3–4 hours in Lagos), high transport costs (25–30% of low-income budgets; NBS, 2022), and informal transport dominance (80% of trips via unregulated minibuses). Rural issues include poor connectivity (40% of communities lack motorable roads; RAMP, 2021) and gendered travel burdens (World Bank, 2020).

CASE STUDY – LAGOS BRT: Since 2008, the BRT has cut travel times by 30% for 200,000 daily riders, improving job access by 15% (LAMATA, 2021), but suffers from limited coverage and overcrowding.

Table 1: SWOT Analysis of Nigeria’s Transport System

Strength	Weakness	opportunities	Threats
Growing BRT/rail investments	Underfunded maintenance	Leverage the AFCFTA for cross-border transport	Political instability
High demand for formal transit	Informal sector resistance	Mobile money for fare subsidies	Fuel subsidies removals
Youth workshop potential	Poor inter-agency coordination	PPP models for road construction	Climate risks(flooding)

Source: LAMATA (2021)

GLOBAL LESSONS:

- *China* – Rural road programs increased school enrolment by 12% in beneficiary areas (Chanieabate et al., 2022).
- *South Africa* – Subsidized BRT fares improved affordability (Venter, 2011).
- *Kenya* – Mobility improvements expanded employment and education access for women (Salon & Gulyani, 2010).

- *UK/US* – Fare subsidies and reliable transport access reduced social exclusion (Lucas, 2012; Blumenberg & Ong, 2001).

Findings informed policy recommendations: expand BRT to 100 km, introduce income-based fare subsidies, prioritise rural gravel-road networks, deploy mobile social services, and align transport planning with the National Poverty Reduction Strategy (2021–2025).

OVERVIEW OF FINDINGS

The analysis revealed that transport interventions have demonstrable impacts on poverty reduction through improved accessibility, affordability, and socioeconomic outcomes. Global case studies demonstrate measurable benefits, while Nigeria’s transport sector shows both significant progress (e.g., Lagos BRT) and critical gaps, especially in rural areas.

NIGERIA’S URBAN TRANSPORT OUTCOMES

Urban transport in Nigeria is marked by high costs and inefficiency. Lagos, with over 20 million residents, faces daily congestion and overcrowded informal transport systems. Data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2022) indicate that transport costs consume 25–30% of monthly household income for low-income urban residents — far above the 10–15% affordability benchmark recommended by the World Bank (2020) (see Table 2).

Table 2: Key Urban Transport Indicators (Lagos)

Indicator	Value	Source
Average daily commute time	3–4 hours	LAMATA (2021)
Share of income spent on transport	25–30% (low-income households)	NBS (2022)
Share of trips via informal transport	~80%	LAMATA (2021)
Lagos BRT average travel time savings	30% reduction	LAMATA (2021)
Employment accessibility gain (BRT)	+15%	LAMATA (2021)

Source: LAMATA (2021)

DISCUSSION:

The Lagos BRT system demonstrates that targeted mass transit investments can yield substantial time and accessibility benefits, consistent with findings from Johannesburg’s BRT system (Venter, 2011). However, limited coverage and overcrowding constrain impact. Expansion could further reduce commuting times and increase labour market participation.

NIGERIA’S RURAL TRANSPORT OUTCOMES

Rural areas face critical infrastructure deficits. According to the Rural Access and Mobility Project (RAMP, 2021), 40% of rural communities lack motorable roads, and many are seasonally inaccessible during the rains (see Table 3).

Table 3: Key Rural Transport Indicators (Nigeria)

Indicator	Value	Source
Rural communities without motorable roads	40%	RAMP (2021)
Average distance to nearest secondary school	5–10 km (often by foot)	World Bank (2020)
Average distance to nearest market	8–15 km	NBS (2022)
% agricultural produce lost due to poor roads	15–20%	FAO (2021)

Source: NBS (2022)

DISCUSSION:

Poor rural connectivity results in market exclusion, lower farm-gate prices, and reduced educational attainment, consistent with rural transport–poverty linkages documented in China (Chaniebate et al., 2022). Investment in low-cost, all-weather rural roads could replicate China’s 12%

increase in school enrolment in connected communities.

COMPARATIVE INSIGHTS FROM GLOBAL CASES

The cross-case synthesis using Lucas’s (2012) Transport Disadvantage Framework shows that countries achieving significant poverty reduction through transport share three critical features (Figure 3).

Source: Lucas,(2012)

Figure 3: Common Features of Successful Transport Interventions

- **Infrastructure Investment** – E.g., China’s rural road program (Chaniebate et al., 2022).
- **Affordability Measures** – E.g., South Africa’s BRT fare subsidies (Venter, 2011); UK concessionary fares (Lucas, 2012).
- **Policy Integration** – E.g., Kenya aligning mobility improvements with gender empowerment goals (Salon & Gulyani, 2010).

transport is largely disconnected from national poverty reduction strategies.

SYNTHESIS: IMPLICATIONS FOR NIGERIA

1. **Urban Transport** – Scaling up BRT networks could reduce commute times and transport costs for millions, but affordability must be addressed through targeted subsidies.
2. **Rural Transport** – Prioritising basic road connectivity could deliver **direct economic gains** (lower crop losses, higher prices) and **social gains** (higher school attendance, healthcare access).
3. **Equity Lens** – Addressing gender disparities in mobility could unlock significant latent productivity.

DISCUSSION:

These features are largely absent or fragmented in Nigeria’s policy approach. For instance, while Lagos has invested in BRT infrastructure, affordability mechanisms remain weak, and rural

Table 4: Potential Poverty Reduction Impacts of Recommended Transport Measures

Intervention	Expected Impact (Evidence-Based Estimate)	Source
Expand BRT to 100 km	+20–25% increase in job accessibility for low-income workers	Venter (2011); LAMATA (2021)
Income-based fare subsidy	Reduce transport cost share from 30% to <20% of household income	Lucas (2012)
Rural gravel roads	+10–15% increase in school enrolment; +15% farm-gate prices	Chanieabate et al. (2022)

Source: Chanieabate et al. (2022)

LIMITATIONS

- (1) Reliance on secondary data may obscure localised dynamics.
- (2) Limited disaggregated gender data for rural Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that transport is not merely an enabler of mobility but a driver of social and economic inclusion. In Nigeria, urban transport interventions like the Lagos BRT have yielded measurable benefits but remain limited by scale, integration, and affordability. Rural areas face more severe challenges, where basic road access can transform livelihoods, health, and education outcomes.

By synthesizing global best practices with Nigeria-specific data, the findings underscore three critical points:

1. **Accessibility and affordability are equally important**—transport investments that ignore cost barriers will exclude the poorest.
2. **Spatial equity must guide planning**—addressing mismatches between residential locations and economic opportunities is essential.
3. **Integrated policy frameworks**—linking transport, poverty reduction, and infrastructure development are required for sustainable impact.

If these principles are embedded into national and state transport strategies, Nigeria could significantly reduce poverty and foster inclusive growth by 2030.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

In Urban transport, BRT services should be expanded in Lagos from 22 km to at least 100 km and integrate it with ride-hailing and micro-mobility solutions for last-mile connectivity and the introduction of income-based fare subsidies, modeled on South Africa’s Rea Vaya, to reduce the cost burden on low-income households and finally and upgrade of the informal transport by formalizing danfo operations, implementing safety standards, and regulating fares.

Rural Transport should Prioritize gravel over asphalt for rural roads to reduce construction costs and increase network coverage, following China’s rural road model and the deployment of mobile clinics and educational services via motorcycle ambulances in hard-to-reach communities, especially in the North-East. The development of gender-sensitive transport policies to reduce time poverty for women be encouraged. The establishment of the National Transport Poverty Index to track how transport projects impact poverty indicators across regions and align transport budgets with the National Poverty Reduction Strategy (2021–2025) for coordinated resource allocation. Promotion of Public–Private Partnerships (PPPs) to leverage private sector investment in transport infrastructure is advocated.

REFERENCES

- Alonso-Epelde, E., Garcia-Muros, X., & Gonzalez-Eguino, M. (2023). Transport poverty indicators: A new framework based on the household budget survey. *Energy Policy*, 178, 113517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2023.113517>
- Blumenberg, E., & Ong, P. (2001). Cars, buses, and jobs: Welfare participants and employment access in Los Angeles. *Transportation Research Record*, 1756(1), 22–31. <https://doi.org/10.3141/1756-04>
- Cain, A., & Jones, P. M. (2008). Does urban road pricing cause hardship to low-income car drivers? An affordability approach. *Transportation Research Record*, 2067(1), 47–55. <https://doi.org/10.3141/2067-06>
- Castro, A. B., Ortega, A., & Odamtten, G. (2022). Up around the bend? How transport poverty can lead to social exclusion in a low-income community in Lagos, Nigeria. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 101, 103367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2022.103367>
- Chaniebate, M., He, H., Guo, C., Abrahamgeremew, B., & Huang, Y. (2022). Examining the relationship between transportation infrastructure, urbanisation level, and rural–urban income gap in China. *Sustainability*, 15(10), 8410. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15108410>
- Currie, G., & Delbosc, A. (2011). Transport disadvantage: A review. In G. Currie (Ed.), *New perspectives and methods in transport and social exclusion research* (pp. 15–26). Emerald Group Publishing.
- Diaz Olvera, L., Plat, D., & Pochet, P. (2008). Household transport expenditure in Sub-Saharan African cities: Measurement and analysis. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 16(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2007.05.001>
- Dueñas, M., Campi, M., & Olmos, L. E. (2021). Changes in mobility and socioeconomic conditions during the COVID-19 outbreak. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 8(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-021-00965-0>
- Farrington, J., & Farrington, C. (2005). Rural accessibility, social inclusion, and social justice: Towards conceptualisation. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 13(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2004.10.002>
- Helena, T., et al. (2014). Transport and poverty: A review of the evidence. *International Transport Forum Discussion Papers*, 2014/03. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5jrw1kt8d3zw-en>
- Lagos Metropolitan Area Transport Authority. (2021). *Lagos BRT impact assessment report*. LAMATA.
- Lin, H. (2024). The impacts of income inequality on economic growth in the emerging economies. *Highlights in Business, Economics and Management*, 4, 908–912. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-48817-0_106
- Liu, C., & Bardaka, E. (2020). The suburbanization of poverty and changes in access to public transportation in the Triangle Region, NC. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 85, 102704. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2020.102704>
- Lucas, K. (2011). Making the connections between transport disadvantage and the social exclusion of low-income

- populations in the Tshwane Region of South Africa. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 19(6), 1320–1334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2011.02.007>
- Lucas, K. (2012). Transport and social exclusion: Where are we now? *Transport Policy*, 20, 105–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2012.01.013>
- Luke, R. (2024). Transport-related social exclusion and mobility in developing countries: The South case. *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*, 6, 1199055. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsc.2024.1199055>
- Markovich, J., & Lucas, K. (2011). The social and distributional impacts of transport: A literature review. *Transport Studies Unit, University of Oxford*.
- Middlemiss, L. (2016). A critical analysis of the new politics of fuel poverty in England. *Critical Social Policy*, 37(3), 425–443. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261018316674851>
- Mitric, S. (2013). Urban transport lending by the World Bank. *Research in Transportation Economics*, 40(1), 19–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2012.06.030>
- National Bureau of Statistics. (2022). *Household expenditure and income survey*. Abuja, Nigeria: Author.
- Olojede, O., Yoade, A., & Olufemi, B. (2017). Determinants of walking as an active travel mode in a Nigerian city. *Journal of Transport & Health*, 6, 327–334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2017.06.008>
- Panman, A., & Gracia, N. L. (2022). Tilting and beyond: Evidence from Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. *Land Use Policy*, 120, 106282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106282>
- Rath, A. (2022). Urban poverty and vulnerability in the global South: An alternative multidimensional framework for measurement and targeting. *Regional Science Policy & Practice*, 14(2), 376–396. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rsp3.12493>
- Rodrigue, J. P. (2020). *The geography of transport systems* (5th ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429346323>
- Rural Access and Mobility Project. (2021). *Annual report on rural connectivity in Northern Nigeria*. Abuja, Nigeria: Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development.
- Salon, D., & Gulyani, S. (2010). Mobility, poverty, and gender: Travel choices of slum residents in Nairobi, Kenya. *Transport Reviews*, 30(5), 645–667. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441640903298998>
- Shamshiripour, A., Rahimi, E., Shabanpour, R., & Mohammadian, A. (2020). Dynamics of travelers' modality style in the presence of mobility-on-demand services. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 115, 102626. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2020.102626>
- Sietchiping, R., Permezel, M. J., & Ngomsi, C. (2012). Transport and mobility in sub-Saharan African cities: An overview of practices, lessons, and options for improvement. *Cities*, 29(3), 183–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2011.11.001>
- Sustrans. (2012). *Locked out: Transport poverty in England*. <https://www.sustrans.org.uk/lockedout>
- Tiznado Aitken, I., Palm, M., & Farber, S. (2024). Exploring the interplay of transportation, time poverty, and

- activity participation. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 26, 101175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2024.101175>
- Urry, J. (2007). *Mobilities*. Blackwell.
- Vas, E., & Venter, C. (2012). The effectiveness of bus rapid transit as part of a poverty reduction strategy: Some early impacts in Johannesburg. In *Proceedings of the 31st Southern African Transport Conference* (pp. 619–631). Pretoria: SATC.
- Venter, C. (2011). Transport expenditure and affordability: The cost of being mobile. *Development Southern Africa*, 28(1), 121–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0376835X.2011.545174>
- World Bank. (2002). *Urban transport and poverty reduction*. Washington, DC: The World Bank.
- World Bank. (2020). *Gender disparities in rural transport: A case study of Northern Nigeria*. Washington, DC: The World Bank.
- Zahonogo, P. (2016). Trade and economic growth in developing countries: Evidence from sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of African Trade*, 3(1–2), 41–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joat.2017.02.001>